

CEREBRAL MICRO-BLEEDING SEGMENTATION BASED ON CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS (CNN)

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ABSTRACT

Manual detection of Cerebral Microbleeds (CMB) by radiologists is time consuming and prone to errors. Hence, researchers have developed various Machine Learning techniques to automate this task. The highest performing model on the CMB dataset using Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) achieved a prediction accuracy of 97.78%. The importance of accuracy especially in diagnosis cannot be over emphasized as the patient has so much to lose when there is a wrong diagnosis. These models have been localized by the researchers as they were not deployed to enable radiologists' means to carry out CMB detection remotely. This project was aimed at achieving an improved performance in CMB detection by changing the structure and parameter settings of the CNN model. The final model developed from this project achieved a record accuracy of 98.8% in predicting CMBs.

INTRODUCTION

Advancement in technology over the years has seen increased use of computers in the healthcare sector. Employment of information technology in healthcare has moved from just administrative tasks on patients' medical record and human resource management to more advanced activities such as ailment diagnosis and patient monitoring.

A field of Computer Science which has found wide applicability in health care is Artificial Intelligence (AI). AI deals with developing machines which are capable of mimicking human intelligence. Some of the subfields of AI are Machine Learning, Computer Vision, Natural Language Processing (NLP). (Wayne, Hui, & Alison, n.d.)

Figure 1: Subfields of AI(Marconi, 2016)

Figure 1 above shows the various branches (application areas) of artificial Intelligence (Kulkarni, 2017).

Machine Learning deals with developing algorithms to enable computers to carry out tasks from given input data without being explicit programmed. Common Machine learning algorithms includes Classification, Regression, Clustering, and Dimensionality Reduction.

Machine Learning is composed of many branches most common of which are supervised and unsupervised learning. In supervised learning, it involves trying to find a relationship between input data to known targets (usually established by humans). An example is an objective of this research work which is to collect brain scans that a neuroradiologist has classified into different groups (i.e., CMBorNon-CMB). In contrast to unsupervised learning where no criterion standard images or classifications are used—the computer itself must determine the classes. One example is clustering, in which images are placed in multiple groups based on similarity metrics.(Zaharchuk, Gong, Wintermark, Rubin, & Langlotz, 2018)

According to (Martinez-Ramirez & Greenberg, 2014), Cerebral microbleeds (MBs) are small chronic brain hemorrhages that affects the structural formation of the tiny vessels of the brain. The magnet-like characteristics of blood degradation products provides the possibility of detecting MBs by using specific Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) processes.

This project seeks to assist radiologists in easily diagnosing the presence CMBs from Magnetic Resonance Images (MRIs). Therefore, x-ray images of the brain can be instantly classified as normal (Non-CMB) or abnormal (CMB) with high degree of accuracy. Identifying the presence of CMB manually is the benchmark for assessment. Manual screening of images by clinicians is stressful, time consuming and subjective(dependent on the experience and expertise of the observer).A good example of the efficiency offered by AI tools in diagnosis is Babylon, an AI-powered smartphone app that was developed to assist the NHS by assessing the Health cases of users in the London area based on the symptoms supplied. It then advises the user on the next action to be taken based on the info provided.(Burgess, 2017)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A dataset consisting of 1304 of human labelled Images of fairly even number of CMB and non-CMB images were collected. These images serve as input to the deep learning model.The dataset consisted of images in .mat format. In a research effort aimed to identify the central point is from surrounding neighbours (Wang, et al., 2019)reported that researchers found it difficult for conditions where the width is less than or equal to 51. However, they were able to identify neighbours where the width is greater than 61 with relative ease. The dataset used for this research has images of size 41. The implication of which is that the accuracy of the developed model might be affected as the ground truth established are not 100% guaranteed.

Figure 2: A sample image from the dataset showing CMB and non-CMB images

In this research work, CNN was chosen as the machine learning technique to classify X-ray images of the brain into CMB and non-CMB. Thus, this is a binary classification problem - with only two classes. Feature normalization is carried out on the data set to increase the speed of convergence. Training the model is started with few layers which would initially show underfitting. Hyperparameter tuning is then carried out. This involves gradually increasing the number of layers or the number units in each layer until the model starts showing signs of overfitting (Chollet, 2018) . The final model was built as a sequential model which is a linear stack of layers. The model was built starting with two convolutional layers each with 8 filters. The number of layers and filters were gradually incremented until it began to show signs of overfitting. The final model built consists of 4 convolutional layers with 16, 32, 32 and 64 filters respectively with kernel size of 3 X 3. Max pooling was used after each convolutional layer except after the first with a pooling size of 2 X 2. Zero padding was applied to the convolutional layers to keep the input and output feature maps of the same size and RELU activation to introduce non-linearity. A flatten operation is defined to convert the tensors into vector. This is fed to a dense layer with 128 neurons with RELU activation. It is finally connected to another dense layer with one output to carry out the classification using a sigmoid function. To further improve the model's performance, data augmentation technique is carried out to increase the size of the dataset which helps to reduce overfitting and in turn increase generalization (Nikita, Julien, & Cordelia, 2018). Binary cross entropy is chosen as

the loss function while Adam which is an adaptive learning rate optimizer proved to perform better than others tried during training. Callback was also defined to be used for the models during training helping to give greater control of the training process. Three calls were applied for training all the models; Early Stopping, Model Checkpoint and Reduce on Plateau.

The data split carried out resulted in the distribution of data as seen in the table below

	TRAIN	VALIDATION	TEST	TOTAL
CMB	494	123	24	641
NON-CMB	506	127	30	663
TOTAL	1000	250	54	1304

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3 below shows the model used with training carried out with a maximum of 20 epochs and a batch size of 32 defined. Training ended after 19 epochs in approximately 7 minutes. It ended with validation accuracy of 98.8% as can be seen in the image below.

```

Epoch 1/20
1000/1000 [-----] - 27s 27ms/step - loss: 0.5673 - acc: 0.7200 - val_loss: 0.3697 - val_acc: 0.7960
Epoch 2/20
1000/1000 [-----] - 23s 23ms/step - loss: 0.2345 - acc: 0.8910 - val_loss: 0.1341 - val_acc: 0.9600
Epoch 3/20
1000/1000 [-----] - 23s 23ms/step - loss: 0.1025 - acc: 0.9700 - val_loss: 0.0566 - val_acc: 0.9880
Epoch 4/20
1000/1000 [-----] - 26s 26ms/step - loss: 0.0645 - acc: 0.9860 - val_loss: 0.0447 - val_acc: 0.9840
Epoch 5/20
1000/1000 [-----] - 22s 22ms/step - loss: 0.0780 - acc: 0.9760 - val_loss: 0.0573 - val_acc: 0.9760
Epoch 6/20
1000/1000 [-----] - 23s 23ms/step - loss: 0.0423 - acc: 0.9870 - val_loss: 0.0901 - val_acc: 0.9640
Epoch 7/20
1000/1000 [-----] - 25s 25ms/step - loss: 0.0270 - acc: 0.9900 - val_loss: 0.0326 - val_acc: 0.9840
Epoch 8/20
1000/1000 [-----] - 23s 23ms/step - loss: 0.0219 - acc: 0.9910 - val_loss: 0.0331 - val_acc: 0.9880
Epoch 9/20
1000/1000 [-----] - 18s 18ms/step - loss: 0.0192 - acc: 0.9940 - val_loss: 0.0489 - val_acc: 0.9880
Epoch 10/20
1000/1000 [-----] - 16s 16ms/step - loss: 0.0155 - acc: 0.9940 - val_loss: 0.0364 - val_acc: 0.9920
Epoch 11/20
1000/1000 [-----] - 15s 15ms/step - loss: 0.0143 - acc: 0.9950 - val_loss: 0.0331 - val_acc: 0.9920
Epoch 12/20
1000/1000 [-----] - 17s 17ms/step - loss: 0.0129 - acc: 0.9940 - val_loss: 0.0395 - val_acc: 0.9880
Epoch 13/20
1000/1000 [-----] - 17s 17ms/step - loss: 0.0124 - acc: 0.9970 - val_loss: 0.0337 - val_acc: 0.9880
Epoch 14/20
1000/1000 [-----] - 16s 16ms/step - loss: 0.0116 - acc: 0.9960 - val_loss: 0.0354 - val_acc: 0.9880
Epoch 15/20
1000/1000 [-----] - 22s 22ms/step - loss: 0.0107 - acc: 0.9980 - val_loss: 0.0393 - val_acc: 0.9840
Epoch 16/20
1000/1000 [-----] - 24s 24ms/step - loss: 0.0112 - acc: 0.9980 - val_loss: 0.0332 - val_acc: 0.9920
Epoch 17/20
1000/1000 [-----] - 25s 25ms/step - loss: 0.0100 - acc: 0.9990 - val_loss: 0.0337 - val_acc: 0.9880
Epoch 18/20
1000/1000 [-----] - 23s 23ms/step - loss: 0.0088 - acc: 0.9990 - val_loss: 0.0383 - val_acc: 0.9880
Epoch 19/20
1000/1000 [-----] - 23s 23ms/step - loss: 0.0082 - acc: 0.9990 - val_loss: 0.0371 - val_acc: 0.9880

```

Figure 3: Training process for new model

The training process for this model was set to a maximum of 20 epochs and a batch size of 64. Callbacks were defined as stated in Chapter 4.2.3.1. The training process took about 7 minutes resulting in a validation accuracy of 98%

```
history2=model.fit_generator(datagen.flow(X_train, y_train, batch_size=20),callbacks=model_callbacks, epochs=20,validation_data=
Epoch 1/20
200/200 [=====] - 88s 442ms/step - loss: 7.9623 - acc: 0.5060 - val_loss: 0.0374 - val_acc: 0.9880
Epoch 2/20
200/200 [=====] - 88s 440ms/step - loss: 7.9623 - acc: 0.5060 - val_loss: 0.0374 - val_acc: 0.9880
Epoch 3/20
200/200 [=====] - 83s 416ms/step - loss: 7.9623 - acc: 0.5060 - val_loss: 0.0374 - val_acc: 0.9880
Epoch 4/20
200/200 [=====] - 91s 454ms/step - loss: 7.9623 - acc: 0.5060 - val_loss: 0.0374 - val_acc: 0.9880
Epoch 5/20
200/200 [=====] - 64s 318ms/step - loss: 7.9623 - acc: 0.5060 - val_loss: 0.0374 - val_acc: 0.9880
Epoch 6/20
200/200 [=====] - 56s 278ms/step - loss: 7.9623 - acc: 0.5060 - val_loss: 0.0374 - val_acc: 0.9880
```

Figure 4: Training process after data augmentation on new model

Figure 5: Confusion matrix of new model on test data

The same confusion matrix as shown in the figure above was obtained after data augmentation was carried out.

Comparison to State-of-the-Art Approaches

The efficiency of the developed can be better analyzed by comparing it with state-of-the-art models. (Wang, Jiang, Xiaoxia, Cheng, & Sidan, 2017) developed a 5-layer based CMB model which attained an accuracy of 97.18%. (Wang, et al., 2019) increased the benchmark by producing a model with 97.28% accuracy while the work of (Wang, Tang, Sun, & Zhang, 2019) using densely connected neural network poled an accuracy of 97.78%. The model from this research attained an accuracy of 98.8% outperforming the previous highs.

CONCLUSION

Using convolutional neural networks (CNN), the model developed was able to detect CMB to high degree of accuracy. Thus, by applying deep learning methods, this research has increased the benchmark for models in the detection of Cerebral Micro Bleeds (CMB). Extracting features from Xray was complex issue for the neural network model as CMB is Gaussian distribution. Increased data size with high resolution could bring about even higher performance. This demonstrates the application of deep learning in cosmological problems. For the future, it would also be relevant to increase the number of labels being classified by the CNN model considering aspects such as white and grey matter rather than just the binary classification presently being carried out; CMB and non-CMB.

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